

Misleading meta-analysis on vitamin C and critically ill patients by Langlois (2019)

Harri Hemilä¹

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<https://pubpeer.com/publications/D661E94CBDF6C6A9C04B8ACCD32DFC#1>

The address of this version is: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19855543>

There was no response by the authors by 2026.

See a parallel description of flaws in another report

by Hill A, Stoppe C, Adhikari NKJ, Heyland DK, et al. (2019)

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/32102297>

<https://doi.org/10.3390/nu12020586>

<https://www.mdpi.com/2072-6643/12/2/586/s1> Detailed description of the errors

<https://zenodo.org/records/19733780> Detailed description of the errors

See a parallel description of flaws in another report

by Hill A, Langlois P, Adhikari NK, Heyland DK, Stoppe C, et al. (2018)

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19789077>

See a parallel description of flaws in another report

by Hill A, Stoppe C, et al. (2023)

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19861834>

Comment on:

Langlois PL, Manzanares W, Adhikari NKJ, Lamontagne F, Stoppe C, Hill A, Heyland DK.

Vitamin C Administration to the Critically Ill: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis.

JPEN J Parenter Enteral Nutr. 2019;43(3):335-346.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/30452091>

<https://doi.org/10.1002/jpen.1471>

An important goal in modern biomedicine is specificity. The strength of the RCT is that the difference between the trial groups can be specifically attributed to the intervention that is being tested.

The title of a recent review in JPEN by Langlois et al. indicated that their focus was the specific effect of vitamin C for critically ill patients (1). Furthermore, the abstract describes that they searched “for RCTs comparing vitamin C, by enteral or parenteral routes, with placebo or none, in intensive care unit (ICU) patients.” However, Table 1 of the review shows that only two (2,3) of the

1 Harri Hemilä, MD, PhD

Department of Public Health, University of Helsinki, Helsinki, FINLAND.

<https://www.mv.helsinki.fi/home/hemila>

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4710-307X>

<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/?term=hemila+h>

<https://scholar.google.com/citations?user=2mkomzUAAAAJ>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17085738> Reports on scurvy uploaded to Zenodo by Harri Hemilä

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19791426> Misleading and erroneous papers on vitamin C; a list by Harri Hemilä

included 11 trials were vitamin C trials. Nine of the included trials administered vitamin C with vitamins A, B, or E, or with selenium, zinc, etc. Thus, those nine trials do not test the specific effect of vitamin C. The other substances can have negative or positive effects of their own, biasing the analysis of vitamin C effects.

Langlois et al. wrote that the length of ICU stay “was reported by 8 of the 11 RCTs, but only 5 trials reported data as mean and SD, allowing statistical aggregation” (1, p. 339). Only one of the five trials included in that analysis tested vitamin C alone (3). Thus, the four other trials tested vitamin C together with other substances.

We undertook our own meta-analysis of vitamin C for critically ill patients and found 17 controlled trials that were informative about the specific effect of vitamin C on the length of ICU stay (4). Only two (2,3) of the 17 trials which we identified, were identified by Langlois et al. (1). Furthermore, those two trials (2,3) were so small, with a total of just 52 patients, that we considered them to be uninformative and excluded them from our meta-analysis on vitamin C and the length of ICU stay. The 17 trials that we included either reported the SD, or we were able to impute the SD, so that we could calculate the P-value for each of the 17 comparisons. Restricting our analysis to 12 trials with 1766 patients, we calculated that vitamin C reduced the length of ICU stay by 7.8% ($p = 0.00003$). We calculated the effect of vitamin C on the relative scale, since there is strong evidence that the relative scale better captures the effects on duration (5,6).

In their abstract, Langlois et al. write that no effect of vitamin C was found on the length of stay in ICU (1). However, our review shows that restricting the analysis to trials of vitamin C alone, carrying out the search thoroughly, and using the relative scale can lead to very different conclusions about the effects of vitamin C on the length of ICU stay (4).

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